

The Impact Of Inflation And Monetary Policy On Exchange Rate.A Case Study Of Pakistan

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Abstract: *The recent continuous depreciation of the Pakistani rupee has sparked debate over the causes of this phenomenon. Inflation and monetary policy have been popular suspects. The research focuses on how monetary policy and inflation affect exchange rates. This study used a data set collected from the WDI, IMF and Pakistan economic survey that covered the years 1980 to 2019. The dynamics of the short and long term of the correlation were investigated using an ARDL model and a Bounds test of cointegration. The findings show that tight monetary policy has a long-run depreciating effect on the local currency, regardless of the monetary policy tool utilized. Inflation as predicted, depreciates the currency over time. The results of the causality test show that monetary policy and inflation do have an effect on exchange rate. It also demonstrates bidirectional inflation and exchange rate correlations as for inflation and money supply. This thesis recommends keeping exchange rate stable, more focus should be placed on inflation control. Money supply has also become highly significant in this model. This suggests that the State bank of Pakistan should maintain a sharp look on the excess money supply to keep inflation under control and the rupee stable.*

Keywords: Exchange rate, inflation, monetary policy , Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL), money supply

Introduction

Exchange rate (ER) is one of the important variables in macroeconomics and it has been studied vastly in literature due to increase in trade between countries for the last some years. ER determines the value of imports and exports because of its impact on the return of the trade. Therefore, governments of the developing countries have always tried to make ER stable. Developing countries are known to be heavily import dependent and due to this reason their currencies face depreciation. Depreciation impacts the local and domestic businesses because they are dependent on intermediate goods and raw materials for their production. Due to the repercussion of ER on imports and exports, there is the repercussion on economic growth rate too. In 1973 Bretton Woods System was demised and countries started

abandoning the system of Managed exchange rate (MER) and shifted towards Flexible exchange rate (FER) system. The exchange rate (ER) is determined by the demand and supply of a country's currency in relation to the currencies of other nations. ER started to be affected easily and become exposed to volatility because it is now easily impacted by supply and demand factors of any currency. Due to the effect of demand and supply of the currencies, ER has become one of the volatile variables in macroeconomics. Therefore, there have been attempts by different scholars to capture the effect of macroeconomic variables fluctuations on ER. There are documented instances of both cross-country and nation-specific research focused on investigating the impact of diverse factors on ER.

According to **Ebiringa and Anyaogu (2014)** there are theories that have linked ER with interest rate (IR) and Consumer Price Index (CPI), these theories are International Fischer Effect (IFE), Mundel Fleming and Purchasing Power Parity (PPP). In IFE and PPP shows the impact of CPI and depreciation on the domestic currencies of the countries. Theories have been suggesting that the countries which have high IR will have depreciation in their currencies when the nominal IR increases. Also, the countries which have IR will have high CPI and vice versa. To assess the long-term and short-term relationships among ER, economic growth, CPI, IR, and broad money supply using Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) and Bound Testing. This study aims to identify the effects of CPI, IR, money supply, and economic growth in both the long run and short run for a specific nation, namely Pakistan.

2 Literature Review

Ali et.al (2015) conduct a study to empirically analyses the outcome of money supply, interest rates also inflation and exchange rates of Pakistan. They conclude that in both short as well in long run, there exist a correlation amongst exchange rate and in inflation. When there is increase in interest rates and supply of money in the economy, then it drive result huge increase in price levels also which leads to enhance exchange rate.

By applying the two-stage least square technique, Siddiqui Afridi and Mehmood (1996) investigate the behaviour of exchange rate in Pakistan from 1960 to 1994. According to this research, trade liberalization encourages currency appreciation. On the other hand, the data suggest that trade terms have a minor impact on rate of exchange.

Most countries have recently experience persistent inflation and fluctuation in real interest rate and exchange rate as observed by Precious WedagaAllor (2020), as the recent increase in free trade between countries, the most critical and important macroeconomic indicator is exchange rate which has been extensively analysed in previous literature. Exchange rate affects the value of exports and imports because they have an impact on international trade returns. Moreover, finding shows that the inflation led to decrease the value of local currency against international currency, and monetary policy (contractionary) which appreciate the currency in long term, while Ndungu (1997) concluded that inflation and exchange rate fluctuations have an impact on each other.

Another study Achsani et al (2010) It was explained that there is a strong relationship between actual exchange rates and inflation in Asian countries. Compared to countries in the European Union and North America, managing inflation or being sensitive to it presents more difficulties because of the Asian region's significantly more effective exchange rates.

As a result, the central banks of Asian countries should consider exchange rate as an important indicator to control inflation. However, Kamin&Kalu (2003) concluded that inflation gives much greater response to exchange rate in Latin America than in the Asian region, this response is due to trade and openness and other economic activities.

Exchange rate volatility refers to the unexpected fluctuation of exchange rate higher or lower over a specified period as Arize et al (2008) critically examined the influence of the volatility of rate of exchange on the export activities to eight economies of the Latin American by employing Co-

integration and VECM econometrics techniques. They revealed that real exchange rate volatility has negligible impact on short as well as in long-run demand for export in these countries. At the same period Egwaikhide and Udoh (2008) Additionally, evaluate the impact of inflation and exchange rate volatility on foreign direct investment (FDI) in Nigeria during these periods. The results show that FDI in Nigeria is negatively impacted by both inflation uncertainty and currency rate volatility.

Saeed et al. (2012) Analyse the factors influencing Pakistan's exchange rate. Data was gathered every month between January 1982 and April 2010. To perform empirical analysis, this study makes use of ARDL and error correction models. The findings show that the money supply is substantial and influences exchange rates favourably over the long run. However, money growth has no immediate effect on Pakistani exchange rates.

3 Empirical Model Specification

$$lnexer = \beta_0\beta_1lnir + \beta_2ln CPI + \beta_3gdp + \beta_4lnms + \varepsilon_t \quad (1)$$

LnER = log of ER,

LnIR = log of IR,

LnCPI = log of consumer price index, which is proxied for CPI,

Gdp = gross domestic product and

LnMS = log of money supply and ε_t is the error term.

Nkoro and Uko (2016) define a non-stationary series as a stochastic process that displays structural breakdowns or a unit root. If the standard deviations of a time-series dataset change with time, it is deemed non-stationary (Gujarati and Porter, 2009). When putting an ARDL model into practice, the integration order of the different series used is crucial. No variable will be categorised as an I(2) series, as was previously stated. The stationarity of the variables is evaluated in this study using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller criterion. The existence of a unit root inside a series is indicated by the ADF test. This test is more resilient than the traditional Dickey-Fuller test since it is still valid even when correlated errors are present.

$$\Delta Y_t = \gamma_0 + \rho_1 Y_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^n \gamma_i \Delta Y_{t-i} + u_t \quad (2)$$

Δ represents the difference operator. The null hypothesis for the test states that the series follows a unit root process. This is equal to declaring that $\rho_1 = 0$. A failure to reject the null hypothesis suggests that the series is not stationary. This analysis will be run on all of the variables in the model. The Phillip-Perron test will serve as an additional check for stationarity.

3.1 ARDL bounds test of co-integration:

Cointegration tests are necessary to identify long-run correlations between variables. Granger (1981) and Engle and Granger (1987) defined the notion. The occurrence of cointegration provides a statistical foundation for running an error-correcting model. The error correction model describes the short- and long-run dynamics of variable interactions. In this study, the ARDL limits test of co-integration established by Pesaran et al (2001) will be applied. This method is employed because it offers various advantages over other traditional Johanson co-integration tests. For starters, no unit root pre-testing is necessary, and various variables may have different optimal lags (Ozturk and Acaravci, 2010).

$$\Delta lner_t = a + \sum_{j=1}^n b_j lner_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} \Delta X_{t-j} + \gamma lner_{t-1} + \beta_i X_{t-1} + u_i(3)$$

$i, t, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$;

i represents the coefficient number, j denotes the lag number, and t indicates the time period. The vector

X signifies the collection of independent variables specified. The short-run parameters are represented by c_{ij} , whereas the long-run parameters are denoted by β_i , and Δ refers to the difference parameter.

3.2 Error Correction model:

If the bounds test detects co-integration in the model, the ARDL model is re-parameterized as an error correction model that takes into account both long-term and short-term relationships. Equations 4 and 5 show the short-term and long-term ECM, respectively.

$$\Delta lner_t = a_0 + \gamma_1 lner_{t-1} + X_{t-1}\beta + u_t \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta lner_t = + \sum_{j=1}^n b_j lner_{t-j} + \sum_{j=1}^n c_{ij} \Delta X_{t-j} + \beta_i X_{t-1} + \phi ECT_{t-1} + u_i \quad (5)$$

The error correction term, designated by ECT_{t-1} , has a coefficient of ϕ . This phrase is known as ECT_{t-1} . The coefficient represents the degree to which long-term performance disparities are addressed with each iteration. It is expected that this coefficient will be statistically significant and negative.

For the results to be valid, the model must be heteroscedastic and autocorrelation-free. Additionally, the models must maintain dynamic stability. Autocorrelation will be detected using the Breusch-Godfrey test, whereas heteroscedasticity will be identified using White's test. To assess the dynamic stability of the model, the CUSUM and CUSUM squared graphs will be used.

3.3 Causality test:

The research also seeks to determine the causal relationships among the exchange rate, monetary policy, and CPI variables examined in this study. This objective is substantiated by the literature's findings. Most authors have focused on the impact of the exchange rate on the CPI, rather than the direction of causation that this research investigates. The aim of this study is to explore the potential for long-run reverse causation among these variables within the context of the Pakistani economy.

The study will utilize the approach developed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995) to assess long-run causation between time series variables. It is important to note that applying traditional Granger causality tests, as proposed by Granger (1969), to co-integrated series may lead to misleading results (Aziz et al., 2000). According to the findings of Toda and Yamamoto (1995), the validity of Granger causality F-statistics is compromised if the series are perfectly correlated and not normally distributed. The Toda and Yamamoto (1995) test can be conducted regardless of whether the level VARs are co-integrated. This testing methodology involves estimating an augmented VAR (p + d) model, where p represents the optimal lag length for the initial VAR, and d indicates the highest level of variable integration. The testing process is divided into two phases. In the first phase, the optimal lag length of the VAR and the maximum order of integration d are determined. In this study, the Akaike Information Criteria (AIC) is employed to ascertain the optimal lag length. The subsequent step involves calculating the VAR (p + d) system and performing the necessary causality tests.

Focusing solely on the key variables pertinent to this research, the equations for the Toda and Yamamoto (1995) test are as follows:

$$lner = \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} a_{1i} lner_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \beta_{1i} lncpi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \phi_{1i} lnir_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \varphi_{1i} lnms_{t-1} + u_{1i} \quad (6)$$

$$lncpi = \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \beta_{1i} lncpi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} a_{1i} lner_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \phi_{1i} lnir_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \varphi_{1i} lnms_{t-1} + u_{1i} \quad (7)$$

$$lnir = \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \phi_{1i} lnir_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} a_{1i} lner_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \beta_{1i} lncpi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \varphi_{1i} lnms_{t-1} + u_{1i} \quad (8)$$

$$lnms = \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \varphi_{1i} lnms_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} a_{1i} lner_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \beta_{1i} lncpi_{t-1} + \sum_{i=1}^{k+d} \phi_{1i} lnir_{t-1} + u_{1i} \quad (9)$$

A Wald test based on these estimates can be used to investigate the many directions of causality. The null hypothesis will be rejected if the test statistic's p-value is less than the set significance level.

4 Result and Discussion

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test at level

Variables	ADF test		PP	
	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value
Lner	-1.152253	0.6847	-0.936725	0.7657
lnIr	-2.655256	0.0912	-2.112243	0.2411
Lncpi	-2.688306	0.0851	-2.886334	0.0561
Gdp growth	-3.924079	0.0044***	-3.860525	0.0052***
Lnms	-1.295465	0.6221	-1.273430	0.6322

Note: ***, **, * shows significant level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

4.1 Unit Root test at First Difference:

When the stationary of the variables at the first level cannot be determined, we can then proceed to the first difference of the unit root test to assess the stationarity of the variables.

Table4.2: Unit Root Test at First Difference

Variables	ADF test		PP	
	t-stat	p-value	t-stat	p-value
Lner	-4.359904	0.0013***	-4.465423	0.0010***
lnIr	-3.694592	0.0082***	-3.694962	0.0082***
Lncpi	-6.114672	0.0000***	-6.113167	0.0000***
Gdp growth	-----	-----	-----	-----
Lnms	-5.484980	0.0001***	-6.880668	0.0000***

Note: ***, **, * shows significant level at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively

Tables 4.1 and 4.2 show the results of the stationarity tests for the variables. The findings show that GDP growth is significant at the level, but all other factors, including the exchange rate (ER), interest rate (IR), consumer price index, and money supply, are not significant. Furthermore, Table 1b shows that all variables, including ER, IR, the consumer price index, and money supply, are significant at the first difference. As a result, stationarity is proven at both the level and first difference, allowing for the use of the ARDL technique.

4.2 Bound Test:

Table 4.2.1: Bounds Test Results

T- Statistics	Value	K
F-Statistics	3.825258	4
Critical value bounds		
Significance	I(0) bound	I(1) bound
10%	2.45	3.52
5%	2.86	4.01
2.5%	3.25	4.49
1%	3.74	5.06

Table 4.2.1 presents the bounds test value, which determines the existence of long-run relationships or co-integration results. The Akaike Information Criteria and the Hannan and Quinn Information Criterion (HQIC) suggest optimal lags of three, while Schwarz's Bayesian Information Criterion

recommends a single lag. In this study, I employed a maximum lag order that reflects the findings of optimal lag selection. The Bounds test for cointegration is conducted on the ARDL model of order ARDL (4,4,4,2,3). The F-statistics value indicates the presence of a long-run relationship, as it exceeds both the lower and upper bounds at the 10% significance level. Consequently, this test confirms the existence of co-integration among the variables, signifying a long-run relationship among them. Therefore, we proceed to utilize the error correction model, which provides estimates for both the long run and short run.

4.3 Auto Regressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) Results:

4.3.1 Short- run ARDL Results:

Table 4.3.1: Short-run ARDL Result

Depended variable Log ER				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	T- statistic	P-value
D(lner(-1))	-0.90617	0.303620	-2.98455	0.0098***
D(lner(-2))	-0.708679	0.254486	-2.784743	0.0146***
D(lner(-3))	-0.408551	0.270282	-1.511575	0.1529
D(lnir)	0.388143	0.122341	3.172630	0.0068***
D(lnir(-1))	-0.017828	0.103339	-0.172517	0.8655
D(lnir(-2))	0.227405	0.104952	2.166752	0.0480**
D(lnir(-3))	-0.345205	0.091033	-3.792073	0.0020***
D(lncpi)	-0.006903	0.028870	-0.239093	0.8145
D(lncpi(-1))	-0.092033	0.041867	-2.198225	0.0453**
D(lncpi(-2))	0.071802	0.041104	1.746840	0.1026
D(lncpi(-3))	-0.087841	0.038187	-2.300293	0.0373**
D(GDP)	-0.017561	0.007341	-2.392200	0.0313**
D(GDP(-1))	0.017502	0.007802	2.243166	0.0416**
D(ms)	-0.008525	0.004459	-1.911802	0.0766
D(ms(-1))	0.002338	0.005903	0.396093	0.6980
D(ms(-2))	-0.008584	0.004320	-1.986946	0.0669
ECT(-1) or cointEq(-1)	-0.170894	0.044907	-3.805478	0.0019***
R-Square= 0.999		Adjusted R-Square= 0.997		

Note:- ***, **, * denote 1%, 5% and 10% significant level

Table 4.3.1 shows the short-run results for the association between the variables. The results show a positive relationship between interest rates and exchange rates (ER). In contrast, inflation, measured by the Consumer Price Index (CPI), has a negative and considerable impact on ER. Furthermore, GDP is significant in the short run. The influence of money supply on ER is discovered to be minimal. Furthermore, Table 4.3.1 shows the short-run findings together with the Error Correction Term (ECT) value, which is significant and has a negative coefficient, indicating the presence of co-integration.

4.3.2 Long- run ARDL Results:

Table 4.3.2: Long Results of the ARDL

Depended variable Log ER				
Variable	Coefficient	Standard error	T- statistic	P-value
IR	-0.061251	0.393668	0.155591	0.8786
CPI	0.320200	0.216720	1.477479	0.1617
GDP	-0.362492	0.056065	-6.465573	0.0000***

MS	1.729773	0.745222	2.321150	0.0359**
C	-0.741311	3.809979	-0.194571	0.8485
R-Square= 0.999		Adjusted R-Square= 0.997		

Note:- ***, **, * denote 1%, 5% and 10% significant level

Table 4.3.2 shows the long run from independent variables to dependent variable. In this estimates IR is insignificant on ER in the long run. While inflation in which CPI is the proxy for it so it is also insignificant effect on ER in the long run. Gross domestic product is significant and negatively related to ER so 1% change in GDP effects 0.362492% to decrease ER. In the increase of GDP the exchange rate is appreciated while due increase in money supply the exchange rate is depreciated.

Money supply shows the positive and significant effect on ER, so 1% change in money supply effects to increase 1.729773 in ER, due increase in money supply the exchange rate is depreciated.

4.4 Diagnostic Tests:

Table 4.4: Diagnostic test Results

Test	Probability Chi-square
Heteroscedasticity	0.1158
Serial correlation LM test	0.2328
Normality test	0.699501

Table 4.4 shows the diagnostic test for heteroscedasticity using the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test, which shows that the chi-square value has a probability greater than 5%, confirming homoscedasticity in the model. Similarly, the Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey test is used to evaluate serial correlation, demonstrating its lack in the model. The normality test shows that the data is regularly distributed, with a p-value greater than 5% in this analysis. To assess stability, we use the cusum and cusum square graphs, which are shown below:

Cusum test

Cusum Square Test

Finally, the Cusum and Cusum square test shows that the variable Is stable in relationship.

4.5 Granger Causality Test Results:

Table 4.5: Granger Causality Test Results

Null Hypothesis	P-value
Lncpi does not Granger cause lner	0.1774
Lner does not Granger cause lncpi	0.8297
Lncpi does not Granger cause lner	0.3016
Lner does not Granger cause lncpi	0.5962
Lnir Granger cause lner	0.0001***
Lner does not Granger cause lnir	0.0791
Lnms Granger cause lner	0.003***
Lner does not Granger cause lnms	0.8092
Lncpi does not Granger cause lnir	0.2510
Lnir does not Granger cause lncpi	0.0515
Lnms does not Granger cause lncpi	0.1160
Lncpi does not Granger cause lnms	0.1056

Table 4.5 shows the Toda and Yamagata Granger causality test is used which indicates that which variable cause the other variable or also to show uni-directional or bi-directional or no causal relation. According to this test if the probability value is less than 5% then reject null hypothesis. In the above table money supply granger cause ER so unidirectional causality occurs from money supply to ER. Similarly, interest rate is also granger cause ER, so unidirectional causality appears. While in the remaining variables there is no granger causality as well as bidirectional causality is also not appeared.

5 Conclusion:

The recent and ongoing depreciation of the Pakistani rupee has ignited discussions regarding the underlying causes of this occurrence. The Consumer Price Index (CPI) and monetary policy have emerged as prominent factors of interest. Consequently, this research centers on examining the impacts of CPI and monetary policy on exchange rates (ER). Furthermore, this study explores the causal

relationships among CPI, exchange rates, and monetary policy. The primary aim is to enhance the understanding of the interactions between these elements to facilitate the development and implementation of effective policy measures. This investigation utilized a dataset sourced from the World Development Indicators (WDI) database and the Pakistan Economic Survey, encompassing the years from 1980 to 2019. The long-term and short-term dynamics of the relationships were analyzed using an Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model and a Bounds test for cointegration. A long-run causality assessment was conducted employing the augmented Granger causality test as proposed by Toda and Yamamoto (1995). The results indicate that, in the short term, CPI positively influences the exchange rate, while the money supply has an insignificant effect on the exchange rate. Additionally, GDP and interest rates also contribute to the appreciation of the exchange rate in the short term. In contrast, the long-term analysis reveals that only GDP and the money supply significantly affect the exchange rate, with the other variables showing no significant impact. An increase in GDP leads to an appreciation of the exchange rate, whereas a rise in the money supply results in depreciation. The Granger causality results demonstrate a unidirectional causality from interest rates to exchange rates, as well as from the money supply to exchange rates, with no evidence of bidirectional causality among the variables. To maintain stability in exchange rates, greater emphasis should be placed on controlling CPI. Initiatives aimed at stabilizing CPI will contribute to the stabilization of exchange rates. The depreciation of the currency is undermining the strength of the Pakistani rupee in the long term. In the short term, a stringent monetary policy is shown to enhance the value of the local currency. Therefore, while employing monetary policy to stabilize exchange rates, it is crucial to proceed with caution.

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Appendix

Secondary data has been taken from the period 1980 to 2019 from World Bank Development Indicators data set for Pakistan and the Pakistan Economic Survey. This time frame was chosen based on the availability of data.

Variables	Denoted by	Measured in	Sources
Dependent Variable			
Exchange Rate	ER	Domestic Currency Per Unit U.S Dollar, End of Period	IMF
Focused Variables			
Broad Money	MS	Broad Money (% of GDP)	WDI
Interest Rate	IR	Interest rate (%)	Economic Survey of Pakistan
Consumer Price Index	CPI	Inflation, Consumer Price (annual %)	WDI
Control Variables			
Growth of Gross Domestic Product	GDP	GDP Annual (%)	WDI

Graphical Analysis:

We done graphical analysis also to check the trends of the variables. Following figures shows the trend of variables separately.

